

ASTRONOMY & MATHEMATICS IN THE INDIAN CLASSICAL AGE

A THESIS SUBMITTED TO THE UNIVERSITY OF MUMBAI

FOR M. A. IN HISTORY

SUBMITTED BY

SUYASHDEEP SASON

UNDER THE GUIDANCE

OF

DR. GAURAV S. GADGIL

DEPARTMENT OF HISTORY

K. J. SOMAIYA COLLEGE OF ARTS AND COMMERCE

VIDYAVIHAR, MUMBAI- 400077.

UNIVERSITY OF MUMBAI

JANUARY 2024

Table of Contents

ABSTRACT	3
INTRODUCTION	4
ASTRONOMY	6
ŚULBA SŪTRAS.....	6
DAWN	7
NEW BELIEFS	8
ECLIPSES	8
UNITS, MEASUREMENTS & CYCLES.....	9
REVOLUTIONS & ORBITS	10
SIDEREAL ROTATION & FASCINATING UNITS	13
HOW FAR COULD WE SEE?	14
PRECESSION.....	17
TRANSITS.....	18
PLANETARY CONJUNCTIONS	19
SPREAD.....	21
INSTRUMENTS.....	21
MATHEMATICS	24
ORIGIN	24
VEDIC ERA	24
VEDIC BRICK FIRE ALTARS.....	25
TOPICS.....	27
PYTHAGORAS BEFORE PYTHAGORAS.....	27
SQUARE ROOT OF 2	27
Π (PI)	28
RISE OF JAIN AND BUDDHIST MATHEMATICS	29
INFINITY.....	30
STYLES	30
ORAL TRADITION	30
MEMORIZATION	31
WRITTEN TRADITION	31
GOLDEN ERA	33
THE LOOK OF IT	34
WRITING MATERIAL.....	35

ALGEBRA	35
MATHEMATICIANS & THEIR CONTRIBUTIONS.....	37
ĀRYABHAṬA.....	37
VARAHAMIHIRA.....	42
BRAHMAGUPTA.....	43
BHĀSKARA I.....	45
DECIMAL NUMBER SYSTEM	46
INJUSTICE	46
CONCLUSION.....	47

ABSTRACT

India – a land of stargazers and storytellers. Being one of the oldest civilizations in the world, our culture has been rich in not one but many disciplines. Astronomy and mathematics are two such fields in which we achieved remarkable prowess, many of them being the first of their kind, but we did not always get the recognition or credit we deserved. More than recognition or credit, this paper focuses on something more important, or rather the most important, and that is – true knowledge. Because although knowledge is divine, it can do a lot of injustice if not served in the right manner with the right facts. There is ample knowledge and narration of our history out there. However, these narrations have been distorted over the course of time due to invasions from outside and different cultures settling and making India their home. Somewhere, amidst all this, our true history got suppressed. This paper discusses the fine achievements and progress of India as a culture in the disciplines of astronomy and mathematics from its origins till the Classical Age (400-1200 CE), a time in which it flourished and reached its peak. It also talks about the injustice done to it due to the distortion of the narration of our history done by the West and transports the reader on a journey through time and in space with the honest purpose of educating the right knowledge and mind-boggling facts about our very own ancient men of science.

INTRODUCTION

The true inspiration behind this paper is the ‘Father of Indian Mathematics’ – Āryabhaṭa (c. 476-550 CE). His achievements and milestones were the true drive that invoked a huge sense of curiosity in me to know more about the entire history during his time specifically concerning the disciplines of astronomy and mathematics, subjects that I love the most. Therefore, the paper begins with my research in presenting the origins of these fields and then moves further across the years to deep dive into the volcano of scientific data excavated from their manuscripts and other sources.

The paper primarily covers the Classical Age of India (400-1200 CE), although, it begins with the origins and covers important aspects of other ages too, before the Classical Age, especially in the case of mathematics. The paper is split into two main sections to explain both disciplines in their entirety – astronomy is the first one that talks about the roots and origins, taking us through the different topics and milestones achieved in the field of astronomy worth discussing and knowing about, covering the big questions like till where Indians could see in space, what instruments did they use, what did they achieve with it, and so on. The mathematics section begins similarly to the former and then talks about its initial application, touching upon some iconic mathematics topics and terms like the Pythagoras theorem, π (pi), $\sqrt{2}$, and ∞ , especially concerning their origins from the Indian perspective. The paper also talks about the different styles and traditions involved with mathematics, what did their mathematics look like, how did they write it, covering all such intriguing questions we get about the same.

Furthermore, it includes the major contributions on different topics done by the mathematicians of the Classical Age and concludes by speaking about the uncredited and unfair outlook on Indian mathematics and astronomy by the Western world, that led to the creation and establishment of a false narrative of Indian history concerning these two disciplines and also in general.

Being mindful of the average reader’s reluctance to indulge in numbers and calculations readily, I have kept the explanations of concepts as simple as possible and explained most of them at the base level, to ensure there’s a good balance of knowing and learning lightly without feeling technically heavy. Although for some truly mind-blowing facts, I have dived deep into them to share their beauty in a manner that’s not a strain on the brain.

Lastly, Dr. Raj Vedam's teachings in his seminars played a huge role in my paper and I sincerely thank him for his contribution towards uplifting the Indian history and culture.

ASTRONOMY

Today, the world usually doesn't operate harmonically when discussing about subjects like Science and God. When it comes to faith, we have fascinating arguments for both sides, especially when it comes to the origin of life as we know it. Often, it comes down to the point where we cannot agree to disagree, or simply accept that we are yet to know the answers to these forefront existential questions. The early astronomers of India were wise in this case. They were 'woke' in the true sense of the word and they operated harmoniously as if they used those two entities to justify each other. This doesn't come as a surprise, considering we are talking about the time when all the scientific knowledge we know today was originating.

These early astronomers were men of science but devotees of lord *Brahma*. The mighty Āryabhaṭa, the Father of Indian Mathematics, also pays his obeisance to *Brahma* for all his work. In one of the 12 commentaries on his work *Āryabhaṭīya*, Suryadeva says "...because the science which is being set out was due to Him and the mysteries of that science were revealed to Āryabhaṭa on worshipping Him".¹

In earlier times, most of the learning was passed down orally as only the chosen elite could read and write. Since human nature craves entertainment, these learnings were passed on in the form of stories and tales to satiate both knowledge and entertainment for man. Even to date, the art of story-telling is used in different art forms to convey the real messages and teachings of life and anything in general.

ŚULBA SŪTRAS

In the Vedas, the roots of Indian astronomy lie in the 'Śulba Sūtras'. To explain what they are, we need to understand the entire Indian Vedic structure from the top. First, we have the four Vedas, which were large bodies of religious texts that have been orally transmitted since the 2nd millennium BCE via various mnemonic techniques. Vedas are '*śruti*' ("what is heard") and they are different than other religious texts that are '*smṛiti*' ("what is remembered"); they are said to be revelations of sacred sounds and texts heard by ancient sages after their intense meditations.² However, with time, by the end of the Vedic period, i.e., around the middle of the 1st millennium BCE, these Vedas became a little too archaic and obsolete for the common man to relate them with. Therefore, we have the Vedāṅgas that were established, which are auxiliary

sciences meant to assist and help in understanding and interpreting the Vedas in a better manner. There are six disciplines of Vedāṅgas – *Shiksha* (phonetics), *Chandas* (poetic meter), *Vyākaraṇa* (grammar), *Nirukta* (etymology and linguistics), *Kalpa* (rights and rituals), and *Jyotiṣa* (astrology and astronomy). To conserve the sounds of the sacred texts we use the *Śikṣā* and *Chandas*, its meaning is conserved by the use of *Vyākaraṇa* and *Nirukta*, and *Kalpa* and *Jyotiṣa* are used for correctly performing the rights at the correct time. And it is within the *Kalpa*, that we have the Śulba Sūtras (also known as Sulva-sūtras) that are a part of the greater texts called the Shrauta Sūtras. ‘Sūtras’ are ancient texts of aphorisms (a concise statement of a scientific principle).

It is important to understand that we are talking about a time so far in history that the modern bifurcations into astronomy and astrology that we study today were the same back then. In fact, back then, there was nothing like ‘astrology’ at all. Everything was *Jyotisha*, which is the intricate understanding of the skies by calculating the movement of the heavenly bodies mathematically. *Vedanga Jyotisha* is one of the earliest known texts on astrology/astronomy (serves both), whose date goes as far as around 700 BCE.³ All the advances that we see in the field of astronomy happened due to their link and purpose with astrology.

DAWN

The actual study of Indian astronomy roughly began with Āryabhaṭa’s time, as he was one of the first astronomer-mathematicians of our country. He wrote works like *Āryabhaṭīya*, a text which survives and deals with astronomy and mathematics, and the *Āryabhaṭa-siddhanta*, which is known only through references in later works.

Āryabhaṭa’s *Āryabhaṭīya* is divided into four sections –

Gitikā section – Covering topics of astronomy and cosmology like planetary revolutions, orbits, yuga cycles, etc.

Gaṇita section – Dealing with mathematical topics like mensuration, trigonometry, algebra, arithmetic progressions, etc.

Kālakriya section (Reckoning of Time) – dealing with topics about time divisions, year calendars, etc.

Gola section (the Celestial Sphere) – Earth sciences like the motion of the Earth, Moon and planets, etc.

NEW BELIEFS

To start with basics, back then, it was believed that the Sun moved around the Earth, as any layman would feel so, looking at the sky with no prior knowledge whatsoever. However, it was Āryabhaṭa who explained that the appearance of the sun moving from east to west was false, and he explained this with many examples. One of the simplest examples he used was – when a person travels in a boat, the trees on the shore appear to move in the opposite direction (backward). Similarly, the celestial bodies we see in the sky move from ‘east to west’, meaning it’s the Earth that moves around the Sun from ‘west to east’ in an anti-clockwise direction.⁴ It is noteworthy that the Greek astronomer Ptolemy held the belief that the Earth was stationery and immovable. Āryabhaṭa also correctly stated that the moon and the planets shined by reflected sunlight.

ECLIPSES

Āryabhaṭa was also the first one who gave a scientific explanation of the eclipses. He had named the two eclipses *Rahu* and *Ketu*, however, not referring to them as literal demons, but using the names as a metaphor to explain the nature of the eclipses. But the problem is, these facts have been narrated in a very unjust manner in our history by the socialists, Marxists, and the missionaries, as they reduced these momentous discoveries to a mere troll by claiming that Indians were too superstitious to believe that the eclipses were demons. The real key is to see and understand the metaphor behind these things that they couldn’t. When one doesn’t see anything beyond that, their understanding will always remain very trivial and they will find everything merely a myth and nothing else. These stories will remain mere stories if one doesn’t see the wisdom they hold inside them.

Now for instance, in the case of eclipses, Āryabhaṭa explained that the Moon’s orbit and the ecliptic path (the Sun’s path or path around the Sun) had a gap of five degrees between them (see figure below), and it is due to this tilted orbit that there were two points at which the Sun, Earth, and the Moon would line up in a straight line. Accordingly, there would either be a solar

eclipse or a lunar eclipse. And it is for these two phenomena that he gave the names *Rahu* and *Ketu*, as metaphors, not as literal demons. He had even gone further and given formulae telling the length of the Earth's and the Moon's shadows, and the timing and duration of the eclipses.⁵

UNITS, MEASUREMENTS & CYCLES

One of the most initial and foundational aspects of Indian astronomy was the forming of a calculative language that assigned numerical values to Sanskrit alphabets – known as the *Varga* letters. Many know that Hindu cosmology is based on the concept of life cycles where each life cycle is known as a Yuga. It all began with setting up these aspects of periods and cycles in the initial phase, slowly leading to the eventual discoveries in the order of their need and importance. But to truly understand the meaning and the beauty of these discoveries and achievements, and their magnitude, some basic units and measurements should be noted:

1 Yuga cycle = 43,20,000 years

The Yuga Cycle comprises the 4 Yugas:

Satya Yuga – 17,28,000 years

Treta Yuga – 12,96,000 years

Dwapara Yuga – 8,64,000 years

Kali Yuga – 4,32,000 years

The current Kali Yuga as mentioned in the *Āryabhaṭīya*, is said to have started on Friday, February 18, 3102 BCE.⁶

The *Āryabhaṭīya*, by Āryabhaṭa, states that the entire age of the universe comes under a single day of *Brahma* known as a Kalpa. It is equal to 14 Manus, and one Manu itself is equal to 72 yugas.⁷

One Kalpa = 14 Manus

One Manu = 72 yugas

∴ One Kalpa (One *Brahma* Day) = 1008 yugas or 4,35,45,60,000 years

The fascinating part is there is also data on how much time has elapsed since the beginning of the *Brahma* Day:

Time elapsed since One Kalpa → Six Manus + $27\frac{3}{4}$ yugas

= $(6 \times 72) + 27\frac{3}{4}$ yugas [\because One Manu = 72 yugas]

= $432 + 27\frac{3}{4} \times 4320000$ years [\because One yuga = 4320000 years]

= 1,98,61,20,000 years

If you compare this with the above span of One Kalpa (One *Brahma* Day), we clearly see how not even half a day has passed for *Brahma* yet; probably just passed his brunch time.

REVOLUTIONS & ORBITS

The calculation of revolutions and orbits of the planets and celestial bodies was one of the flagship and iconic discoveries of ancient astronomers. They calculated the revolutions of planets (and they calculated this primarily for a yuga), and this data also helped to calculate how much distance a planet covers in an orbit. So, for instance, the revolutions for Sun, Moon, and the Earth in a yuga are 43,20,000, 5,77,53,336, and 1,58,22,37,500 respectively as stated in the *Āryabhaṭīya*.⁸ They are known as ‘revolution-numbers’.

REVOLUTION-NUMBERS AND ZERO POINT

युगरविभगणाः ख्युष्ट, शशि
 चयगियिडुशुछ्लृ, कु डिशिवुएलृप्सु¹ प्राक् ।
 शनि दुड्विध्व, गुरु स्त्रि-
 च्युभ, कुज भदलिभूनुस्, भृगुबुधसौराः ॥ ३ ॥
 चन्द्रोच्च ²जुप्सिध, बुध
 सुगुशिथृन, भृगु जषबिखुछृ, शेषार्काः ।
 बुफिनच पातविलोमा,
 बुधाह्वघजार्कोदयाच्च लङ्कायाम् ॥ ४ ॥

- 3-4. In a *yuga*, the eastward revolutions of the Sun are 43,20,000 ; of the Moon, 5,77,53,336 ; of the Earth,³ 1,58,22,37,500 ; of Saturn, 1,46,564 ; of Jupiter, 3,64,224 ; of Mars, 22,96,824 ; of Mercury and Venus, the same as those of the Sun ; of the Moon's apogee, 4,88,219 ; of (the *sihrocca* of) Mercury, 1,79,37,020 ; of (the *sihrocca* of Venus, 70,22,388 ; of (the *sihroccas* of) the other planets, the same as those of the Sun ; of the moon's ascending node in the opposite direction (*i.e.*, westward), 2,32,226.⁴ These revolutions commenced at the beginning of the sign Aries on Wednesday at sunrise at Lañkā (when it was the commencement of the current *yuga*).

What we are used to in terms of understanding revolutions, years, and days is known as the 'sidereal period' in astronomy and science. Sidereal time is a time scale that is based on the Earth's rate of rotation measured relative to the fixed stars. For instance, the Moon takes 27.3 days to complete one revolution around the Earth. Now, we can understand this because the 'days' we know are 'Earth days'. So, the sidereal revolution of the Moon is 27.3 days. The table below also gives the sidereal period of the planet's revolutions compared to Earth days for our understanding, and it shows the accuracy of Āryabhaṭa's calculations for the same.

Table 2. Mean motion of the planets

Planet	Revolutions in 43,20,000 years	Sidereal period in terms of days		
		Āryabhaṭa I	Ptolemy ¹	Moderns ²
Sun	43,20,000	365.25868	365.24666	365.25636
Moon	5,77,53,336	27.32167	27.32167	27.32166
Moon's apogee	4,88,219	3231.98708	3231.61655	3232.37543
Moon's asc. node	2,32,226	6794.74951	6796.45587	6793.39108
Mars	22,96,824	686.99974	686.94462	686.9797
<i>Śighrocca</i> of Mercury	1,79,37,020	87.96988	87.96935	87.9693
Jupiter	3,64,224	4332.27217	4330.96064	4332.5887
<i>Śighrocca</i> of Venus	70,22,388	224.69814	224.69890	224.7008
Saturn	1,46,564	10766.06465	10749.94640	10759.201

Next, they used this to derive the formula for calculating the orbit of a planet. One minute of an arc (1') of the Moon's orbit is equal to 10 yojanas [1 yojana = 12.8 km (8 miles)], as per their assumptions. As per this, the distance of an orbit of the Moon comes up to 216000 yojanas. Now, the Moon makes 5,77,53,336 revolutions around the Earth in a yuga (as seen in the table above). So, if we multiply the distance of the Moon's orbit by the number of revolutions it makes in a yuga, we get the distance covered by the Moon in a yuga. Thus,

$$(\text{Orbit of the Moon}) \times (\text{Revolutions in a yuga}) = \text{Distance covered by Moon in a yuga}$$

By just simply modifying the formula, we get,

$$\text{Orbit of the Moon} = \frac{\text{Distance covered by Moon in a yuga}}{\text{Revolutions in a yuga}}^9$$

We can understand this formula in many other simpler ways. For instance, if an object makes 20 revolutions around something and covers 100 meters, then to know how much distance it

covers in one revolution, you have to divide 100 by 20. That means one revolution of the object covers 5 meters. Distance covered by any object in 'x' units divided by its number of revolutions will give us the distance covered in one revolution.

And what's even better is how they further renamed the concept of the 'distance of a planet in a yuga' – A yuga is a continuous cycle of life. So, the distance that a planet travels in a yuga is the circumference of the space it covers in its entire lifetime. And this space is what they called the 'Sky' for that planet, and its circumference is the 'Orbit of the Sky'. Hence,

Distance of the planet in a Yuga = Orbit of the Sky (for the planet)

And thus, simplifying the formula, we get,

$$\text{Orbit of the planet} = \frac{\text{Orbit of the Sky (in a yuga)}}{\text{Revolution Number of the planet}} \quad 10$$

This is the way they found the orbits of planets and celestial bodies. Below mentioned are some of them for reference: ¹¹

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Orbit of the sky} &= 57753336 \times 12 \times 30 \times 60 \times 10 \text{ yojanas} \\ &= 12474720576000 \text{ yojanas} \\ \text{Orbit of the asterisms} &= 173260008 \text{ yojanas} \\ \text{Orbit of the Sun} &= 2887666\frac{4}{5} \text{ yojanas} \\ \text{Orbit of the Moon} &= 216000 \text{ yojanas} \\ \text{Orbit of Mars} &= 5431291\frac{132027}{287103} \text{ yojanas} \end{aligned}$$

It seems like the Moon was the most important source and parameter that helped them calculate the measurements of all the celestial bodies. It also served as a basis to find the revolutions of the planets and their orbits. This is logical, as early observers would naturally begin with the Moon due to its proximity and magnitude.

SIDEREAL ROTATION & FASCINATING UNITS

As the Earth's rotation is not constant throughout the year, the duration of the day isn't 24 hours exactly – it's a few minutes shorter or longer. The actual modern value given to the period of a day is 23 hours 56 minutes and 4.091 seconds. Āryabhaṭa even recorded this subject with insane

precision, by calculating the sidereal rotation of the Earth – which was 23 hours 56 minutes and 4.1 seconds according to him:¹²

years. The period of one sidereal rotation of the Earth according of Āryabhaṭa I is $23^{\text{h}} 56^{\text{m}} 4^{\text{s}}.1$. The corresponding modern value is $23^{\text{h}} 56^{\text{m}} 4^{\text{s}}.091$.² The accuracy of Āryabhaṭa I's value is remarkable.

Of the other Indian astronomers who ...

What's interesting is how they used some fascinating units to make their calculations. They linked something as basic as breathing with astronomical geometry. These astronomers used human respiration as a unit to measure the movement of celestial bodies in the sky. One respiration = Four seconds of time, as per them. And the Earth rotates through an angle of $1'$ (one minute of an arc) in one respiration. Another fascinating unit is ' $nṛ$ ' (pronounced *nar*) where $nṛ$ refers to the height of an average man¹³. And $8000 nṛ =$ One yojana (12.8 km)¹⁴. They used this data to calculate the linear diameters and angular diameters of Earth.

Indians very well knew the basic cardinal points of astronomy – the Solstices (Winter and Summer) and the Equinoxes (Vernal and Autumn). Even the reference planes that we use in astronomy like the Horizon, Equator, Ecliptic, etc. and the N, S, E, W directions along with the Zenith (the point on the celestial sphere directly overhead for an observer) were all seen in their writings and understanding.¹⁵ And this is how they formed a mathematical coordinate system to locate the stars and bodies in the sky.

HOW FAR COULD WE SEE?

One big question is always asked when it comes to observational space in general is that how far could the ancient Indians really see. For instance, we know they could see far enough to tell the difference between stars and planets, but how far could they actually see? Did they observe the Andromeda Galaxy? (nearest galaxy to our Milky Way). That's a popular question that's discussed quite often in historical astronomy and there's a really good manner in which this has been described in our history, in the form of a beautiful story that helps us know whether they did or not. For the rest of the world, even after telescopic observations started from 1600s, until very recent the Andromeda was considered as a nebula and not a galaxy. It is only after

the 1920s that it was realized to be a galaxy of its own, just the size of our Milky Way, being 2.5 million light-years away from Earth. Today, if we travel to a remote location, at least a 100 kms away from the city, on a nice new-moon day, we can observe the Andromeda galaxy with our naked eye that looks like a dull rainy cloud at night. Speaking about the Indian story, it is based on the Andromeda constellation and not the galaxy, and it is also an important backstory to the Mahabharata as well.

Sharmistha, a popular princess in Hindu mythology, is the daughter of a *Daitya* (race of Asuras) king, and her friend Devyani is the daughter of the Rishi Shukracharya. One day, at a bath, their clothes get mixed up, Devyani wears her clothes, and Sharmistha gets angry, and pushes her into the well, and that's when she's saved by Yayati (a Chandravamsha king, a key ancestor of the Mahabharata families), and they get married. As punishment, Sharmistha is sent to work for Devyani as a maid and that's when she has an affair with Yayati and has children with him. Devyani is naturally angry and Yayati is cursed with old-age to never enjoy his youth. But since Devyani herself was to suffer the most from this, the boon is modified so that Yayati could swap his old age with any of his sons who were willing to take it. He does get it and enjoys his 1000 years of youth. Later, when his merits are over, he is pushed by the gods from *swarga* and he starts falling.¹⁶ And in the Indian tradition, the Andromeda constellation is identified as Devyani and the 'W' shaped constellation is described as Sharmistha, and the Andromeda galaxy (that looks like a rainy cloud) is Yayati (refer picture below). As Yayati was falling, he was asked by one of the royal sages who he was; they were curious about this mysterious entity falling. On asking if he was on a course to Earth, his response was positive.¹⁷ This is a very fascinating plot about this story that blends with the reality so well as the Andromeda galaxy is indeed on a collision course with the Earth, in 4.5 billion years.¹⁸ Some may believe this to be just a good fairytale coincidence, and some won't. But sometimes, instead of judging something for its truthfulness or practicality, an argument can be concluded at the beauty that both the myth and the fact share a common consequence at the base. On asking Yayati if there was space in heaven where was coming from, he responded that there was enough of it to live on different worlds every week.¹⁹ This is how it became the rishis' expression to convey these facts from such stories that there were thousands of stars and planets revolving inside the Andromeda galaxy.

The above pic shows us five bright stars next to the galaxy. In the story, Yayati is asked by the rishis what the five golden chariots next to him were and where they were taking him (as the constellation also looks like a chariot that's pulling him along), thereby proving that this was indeed the Andromeda galaxy that was being talked about in the story. And that's how we

realize that Indians did observe the Andromeda galaxy. These were the proofs. The Greeks saw the Andromeda constellation and not the galaxy, on which the story of their mythological princess Andromeda is based.²⁰

This is how ancient Indians marinated the facts with these stories so they could serve their purpose in beautiful ways. This is where it becomes really important to understand that the wisdom of our ancient astronomy was not directly written out there to just read and get an understanding of it. As mentioned above, in the eclipse example, it was encoded as metaphors in our great mythological stories and *Puranas*. Now, the definition of ‘myth’ itself is that it’s not a proven reality. If we take it in the literal sense, none of this can be trusted to be true. And it is this infantilization of these myths and stories that prevents us from actually seeing the encoded wisdom and science hidden in them as metaphors. The Indian way of passing on knowledge has always been in the form of stories and tales, where the immersive and engaging elements of storytelling are used to make teaching more interesting and entertaining through which the knowledge is registered better than merely stating the facts. In fact, this is how our ancient Indian mythologies like the Mahabharata have also been written.

A simple reason they could see all this in the sky is because of the times they lived in. Fewer people, no concept of pollution, no smog, no satellites. Simple life, clearer skies. The way we have to travel 100-200 km away from cities for stargazing camps and treks today, they could get the same skies wherever they looked up from.

PRECESSION

Other than observing planets, stars, and something as far as even another galaxy, Indians also observed a phenomenon or a concept called ‘Precession’. It’s a comparatively lesser-known concept but an interesting one. We know that the Earth’s northern axis points directly towards the North Star or the Pole Star ‘Polaris’. However, thousands of years ago – say when the Egyptians were building pyramids – this isn’t what they saw in the skies above the northern axis. During their time, the ‘Thuban’ Star was the Pole Star. This is because along with rotating around itself in 24 hours and revolving around the Sun in 365 days, the Earth is also precessing in the sky, i.e., the axis of rotation of the Earth is also making a slow circle in the sky, which is what ‘precession’ is. The Earth’s axis is also moving, making a circular path in space (as seen

in the pic below). It takes 25,700 years to complete one precession cycle. In the future, by the year 14000 CE, ‘Vega’ will be our Pole Star.²¹

Vṛddha Garga, an ancient astrologer and astronomer, in 500 BCE or even earlier than that, already stated in his observations about this concept and mentioned that the cycle took 36000 years to complete. Similarly, Bhāskara II, during his time, gave an astonishingly close number of 25,461 years for this cycle, which was again, an amazing prowess for Indian astronomers to even be able to figure out complex and slow time-bound concepts like these.

In fact, in the *Sūryasiddhānta*²², there is a detailed explanation of this which also gives us the measurement of how many degrees the axis tilts in a year. The number comes up to 54” (arc-seconds), a figure that is too specific. Values like 48”, 48.6”, and 49.179” were also given by other astronomers like Āryabhaṭa, Bhāskara II, and Patani Samanta respectively. It is truly mind-blowing how they could make such calculations by only using simple instruments made out of bamboo.

TRANSITS

Ancient Indians perfectly knew about the ‘Transits’ – the term given to smaller planets like Mercury, Venus, etc. when they appear as a speckle on the Sun.

They were even capable of knowing when these ‘transits’ would take place.²³ If compared with the West, then it was only during the 1600s when Galileo started using telescopes, and in 1639 is when the first transit of Venus was observed.²⁴ And this was routine in India, much before them.

PLANETARY CONJUNCTIONS

This phenomenon takes place when two planets come closer to each other. It was called ‘*yudh*’, as per the *Sūryasiddhānta*. The book further mentions the conjunctions of various stars and planets with each other. The below picture shows a recent planetary conjunction of Jupiter and Saturn that took place in December 2020²⁵ for reference:

Similar to this, they also observed Lunar Occultations, a situation wherein the Moon obscures or covers a star next to it (from our perspective). So, for the observer, the Moon looks big and the star is a tiny peck next to it. They explained this phenomenon too via mythological stories of Chandra and Rohini.

Comets have also been mentioned to be observed by many ancient astronomers and in many references – from the Rigveda, Ramayana, Mahabharata, Parashara, Vṛddha Garga, Varahamihira – they all have made mentions about comets, which were called ‘*Dhumaketu*’²⁶. Because of the nature of the comets, i.e., having a long periodicity in terms of their path, when the events took place, it was hard to tell which kind of comets they saw or when they were dated. It is only after the 12th century CE that we have reliable information about them.

SPREAD

With the expansion of Buddhism, Indian astronomy reached China too, and there were many works of translations that were done in China during the Three Kingdoms Era (220-265 CE).²⁷ Indian astronomy also had a good influence on Islamic astronomy, especially regarding the timekeeping calendars. Then, Islamic astronomy became a bridge between Indian and European astronomy through the Arab translations of Indian works, especially of Brahmagupta, the 7th-century astronomer-mathematician.

The classical age saw many more astronomers who contributed in different and same areas in the field of astronomy. The list is an inexhaustive one but some of the popular astronomers of this age were Bhāskara I (629 CE), Lalla (8th century CE), Śatānanda (1068-1099 CE), Bhāskara II (1114 CE), Śrīpati (1045 CE), Mahendra Sūri (14th century CE), and Nilakantha Somayaji (1444-1544 CE).

INSTRUMENTS

American historians like David Pingree and Patrick Morrissey created a narrative in the late 80s about how Indians didn't know how to measure the skies. In one of their papers, they concluded, *'We must conclude from this survey that the Indians did not observe the positions of the stars with accuracy; by implication, they also did not observe those of the planets with accuracy.'*²⁸ The reality is the opposite. Ancient Indian astronomers used a lot of instruments to get accuracy in their measurements. They even went on to mention how Indians copied from the Greeks and Babylonians, which has not been even remotely true, considering how our history of using our instruments to measure time and other things goes back 5000 years. For instance, one of the instruments that they used to locate the stars was the 'Golyantra':

The purpose of this instrument was to mark the latitude and longitudes of the celestial bodies. And the way they did this was not through direct measurement (by directly pointing towards it), but rather by going to ‘ecliptical orbits’ (orbits pertaining to eclipses) and in an indirect and complex manner, figuring out the location of the body they wanted to know about.

This goes way back to the Classical Age astronomers. Going back to the origins, starting from the Harappan times, we have the ‘water clocks’ that they used to measure time (3000 BCE). Even the *Vedanga Jyotisha* talks about water clocks. During Āryabhata’s time, there were many instruments they used like the Chaya-Mantra (shadow instrument), Dhanur-Yantra (semi-circle instrument), Chakra-Yantra (circle), Chatra-Yantra (umbrella), are few such examples of them. In fact, Āryabhata also had a globe constructed which he used to possibly figure out the shadows of the Moon, Earth, etc. on each other.²⁹

Varahamihira used something called Chedyaka-yantrani, which he even used to do graphical calculations. Brahmagupta also had a variety of instruments that included different types of sundials (Kapalaka and Karttari) among others.

Brahmagupta wrote the *Brāhmasphuṭasiddhānta*, which is the first surviving Indian text containing a systematic discussion of astronomical instruments, as well as methods of computing astronomical elements from readings taken with them. The instruments include accessories, astronomical instruments for measuring time and observing the celestial bodies, instruments that turn automatically for one day, and ones that rotate perpetually.³⁰

In fact, R.S. Sharma, an Indian historian and Indologist, pointed out an interesting fact that some of the early instruments were made out of wood and bamboo, and were very simple in design so they could not have provided so much precision in measurement. This suggests that the early astronomers probably relied more on their superior computing skills.

MATHEMATICS

ORIGIN

When we talk about the origin of mathematics in India, the Vedas are usually one of the first things that come to our mind. However, the roots of Indian mathematics go much far beyond time, to the infamous Indus Valley Civilization. In actuality, in the later periods, we see how mathematics as a proper subject initially developed as a by-product of astronomical calculations, but during this time, it was not connected even remotely to astronomy. Life was simple back then and so was their math. What is not simple is to figure out how they did it and believe in the amazing accuracy and fineness that have been found in their works.

The people of this period (around 3000 BCE) used mathematics primarily for their constructions, beginning with the making of bricks. We know how the Harappans were popular because of their accuracy and consistency in their brick-sizes, and this is where the first kind of mathematics seems to have originated (that we know so far). The fact that their bricks used to be in a specific ratio (4:2:1) showed that they knew ratios and proportions. Their mathematics was a part of what we call mensuration today, dealing with shapes and basic geometry. Their weights also had a standardized system in the form of ratios, ex. $1/20$, $1/10$, $1/5$, $1/2$, 1, 2, 5, 10, 20, 50, 100, 200, and 500, the initial four being decimal in nature.³¹ They went one level further and developed their own ruler or measuring scale, known today as the *Mohenjo-daro ruler* or the “Indus Inch”. The interesting part about this is that the unit length of this scale was one inch, which was 1.32 inches in length, very close to the present-day inch value. And this scale was divided into 10 parts/inches so $1.32 \text{ inches} \times 10$ gives us 13.2 inches which is, again, very amazingly close to the current measurement of a foot, i.e., 12 inches.³²

VEDIC ERA

We do not entirely know if the mathematical knowledge of the Indus Valley period was passed on to the next period, i.e., the Vedic era. However, the Vedic period is considered to have the concrete roots of Indian mathematics. Three out of four Vedas that we know – Rigveda, Yajurveda, and Atharvaveda, contain topics from different fields of mathematics. The Rigveda consisted of topics from geometry and error correction. The geometry they used was for practical applications and they focused more on the usage than the proof of it. The Rigveda

also mentions the formula to find the area of a circle – πr^2 , indicating that the *rishis* already knew about π . Thus, the first usage of π is also believed to be during this time, with the value being approximately $22/7$. We see evidence of large numbers being used in the Yajurveda. It consisted of the counting of numbers as high as up to 10^{18} .³³ These numbers were used in mantras on different occasions, such as at the end of *annahoma* (food-oblation rite), and they were recited before, during, and after sunrise, using powers from a hundred to a trillion (10^2 to 10^{12}).³⁴ This was a far superior progress when compared to the ancient Greek and Roman cultures, which did not go beyond 10^4 and 10^3 respectively.³⁵ Even when terms like infinity and zero had not mathematically developed yet, they were certainly being used as concepts.

As discussed in the astronomy section, the roots of Indian mathematics, just like astronomy, lie in the Śulba Sūtras. All mathematics that we study about the Vedic period comes from these Śulba Sūtras. They further contain various Sūtras under them, the popular ones being the Baudhāyana, Manava, Āpastamba, and Katyayana.

VEDIC BRICK FIRE ALTARS

These Śulba Sūtras were basically manuals and rules for the construction of Vedic brick fire altars. These brick fire altars had to be made very precisely with the specific measurements assigned to them, and this is how mathematics came into the picture. The image below shows what a Vedic brick fire altar looks like:

The construction for these altars had some fascinating rules – the height of the person constructing it had to be in direct proportion to the surface area of the altar. The alignments were precisely made following the direction of the shadows. The bricks were specifically in multiples of $1/16$ of a unit: $2/16$, $4/16$, and so on. The height of the person constructing it from the sole of the feet to the tips of the fingers when arms stretched high was measured to be 120 angulas (the length of the middle portion of the middle finger), which is equal to one purusha (height of an average man). These altars were made in shapes of animals and birds for different reasons. For instance, a person desiring heaven had to construct the altar in the form of a falcon (as seen above). Shapes like squares, triangles, quadrilaterals were used with specific ratios:³⁶

TOPICS

PYTHAGORAS BEFORE PYTHAGORAS

We can see triangles being used extensively in their constructions, and this is the period when Indians had mentioned expressions of what we know today as the infamous Pythagoras theorem. A statement in Baudhāyana's Śulba Sūtra states,

“दीर्घचतुरस्रस्याक्षण्या रज्जुः पार्श्वमानी तिर्यग् मानी च यत् पृथग् भूते कुरूतस्तदुभयं करोति ॥

In a *Deerghchatursh* (Rectangle) the *Chetra* (Square) of *Rajju* (hypotenuse) is equal to sum of squares of *Parshvamani* (base) and *Triyangmani* (perpendicular)”³⁷

This was much earlier when Pythagoras declared it, who was born in 570 CE, while these Sūtras were written in the first millennium BCE, approximately 700-400 BCE. In fact, the ancient Babylonians also knew the Pythagoras theorem long before him, so it's almost like Pythagoras was the last one to “invent” his own theorem. Everybody in the East practically knew it and was using it routinely. The right angles in the fire altars were made using Pythagorean triplets like (3,4,5), (5,12,13), (8,15,17), and (12,35,37).³⁸

SQUARE ROOT OF 2

The Baudhāyana's Śulba Sūtra also gives the expression for the square root of two, as they needed it for their altar constructions:

Suppose if there's a square with all sides measuring one. We know, as per Pythagoras theorem, that the square of the hypotenuse (the diagonal) would be $1^2 + 1^2 = 2$, and therefore, the hypotenuse will be $\sqrt{2}$.

For this, the expression that they have given is – The measure is to be increased by its third and this [third] again by its own fourth less the thirty-fourth part [of that fourth]; this is [the value of] the diagonal of a square [whose side is the measure]:

$$\sqrt{2} \approx 1 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{3 \cdot 4} - \frac{1}{3 \cdot 4 \cdot 34} = \frac{577}{408} \approx 1.414216$$

And the value has been correct up to 5 decimal places – the true value is 1.41421356...³⁹

Π (PI)

The Āpastamba Sūtras also worked on similar issues and findings like the Baudhāyana. They further talk about concepts like how to make a circle out of a square whose area is the same as that of the square (or vice-versa), i.e., squaring a circle, dividing a segment into seven equal parts, and finding solutions of general linear equations.⁴⁰ In fact, it is while ‘squaring the circle’ when they used π for the first time.

π is a concept that is essential in finding the area of a circle. In our academics, we generally learn π just as a specific value (3.142 or 22/7) and apply it to solve problems. π , by definition, is the ratio of the circumference of a circle to its diameter. Although π has a long history of being used parallelly by many civilizations – such as the Egyptians, Babylonians, Greeks, and Chinese – the Śulba Sūtras reached approximate values of π like 3.088, 3.004, and 3.125. It was Āryabhaṭa who, during his time, gave the value of π correct up to 4 decimal places in his *Āryabhaṭīya*:⁴¹

चतुराधक शतमष्टगुण द्वाषाष्टस्तथा सहस्राणाम् ।

अयुतद्वयविष्कम्भस्यासन्नो वृत्तपरिणाहः ॥ १० ॥

100 plus 4, multiplied by 8, and added to 62,000 : this is the nearly approximate measure of the circumference of a circle whose diameter is 20,000.

This gives

$$\pi = \frac{\text{circumference}}{\text{diameter}} = \frac{62832}{20000} = 3.1416.$$

This value of 3.1416 given by Āryabhaṭa was better than the value of 3.141666 given by Ptolemy. Yet, it is fascinating how Āryabhaṭa, perhaps out of modesty, called his calculation “approximate”. It’s little things like these that make such personalities so loved and respected.

RISE OF JAIN AND BUDDHIST MATHEMATICS

Until the Vedic era, all of mathematics – and science, for that matter – was very much rooted in the religious and ritualistic aspects. One of the reasons we do not see proofs and detailed explanations of their works is because these practices that involved mathematics were operated exclusively by priests and other religious officials. Thus, the mathematics used in them was considered sacred and had to be preserved in that manner. It was not written with the intention of mass education.

It was only after 500 BCE, with the rise of religions like Jainism and Buddhism, that the bond between mathematics and religion loosened. Mathematics got some breathing space and also functioned as a pure science for its own purpose, for what it was. The paradigm of mathematics shifted from altar constructions to higher mathematical computations.

INFINITY

The Jain mathematicians were very fascinated with large numbers and especially with the concept of infinity. Even today, there are fresh discussions about how some infinities are bigger than others, but the Jain mathematicians were the first ones to mention this in their works. They classified infinities into four types with respect to dimensions – If we move in one direction (i.e., one dimension), that's infinity in length. Similarly, there is infinity in area (two dimensions), infinity in volume (three dimensions), and infinity perpetually (infinite number of dimensions).

Not just infinities, they even classified the numbers into three types – *Sankheya* (countable/enumerable), *Asankheya* (uncountable/innumerable), and *Ananta* (infinite). Since they were dealing with these large numbers in their calculations, this is when they started computing squares and cubes of numbers (exponents and powers) to define basic algebraic equations.⁴² Now, although zero as a number was not invented yet, the Jains had pretty much defined the concepts of emptiness or void and addressed it in their calculative works. They gave the name *Shunya*, to this emptiness or void. This is where we see the prehistory and the raw use of zero already being done by the Jain mathematicians of this period.

The contributions of Jain and Buddhist mathematicians became the true link between the Vedic period and the Classical Age of Indian mathematics. This is because the mathematicians of the Classical Age, like Āryabhaṭa, summarized and expanded upon these Jain and Buddhist works.

STYLES

ORAL TRADITION

So far, it's discussed that all mathematical knowledge – or knowledge from any other discipline – was initially passed down orally, as seen during the Vedic period and before that. It was only around 500 BCE, that mathematical knowledge also took a writing form in manuscripts.⁴³ Speaking about the oral tradition, Indian pundits used the skills of memorization and recitation to learn things and pass them down ahead. They could do this not only for a particular set of

chapters but for entire books. This was as per ‘*śruti*’ (“what is heard”), as aforementioned in the Śulba Sūtras.

If we stop for a second, and sink this fact in about this skill, then it is one of the most mind-boggling realities about Indian history – how these learned pundits could memorize entire books and orally pass them down across generations. The pure skill of being able to do something like this is plainly insane. Today, we live in a time when remembering a 10-digit mobile number is a lost skill and our ancestors memorized and narrated books like it’s Monday.

MEMORIZATION

They had some interesting ways to go about this skill. The memorization was not in the simple or linear fashion, the way we have been following it in schools and colleges to pass exams. They had up to 11 forms of memorization, in which some reciting versions were specifically designed to just “proof-read” the texts. *Jaṭā-pāṭha* form of recitation was one type of recitation in which every two adjacent words were recited normally in the ascending order, repeated in the reverse manner, and then again repeated in the original order:

“w1-w2, w2-w1, w1-w2; w2-w3, w3-w2, w2-w3; ...” (‘w’ stands for ‘word’)

In *dhvaja-pāṭha* recitation, the first two and the last two pairs of words were recited and memorized, followed by the next two (from both ends):

“First – Second, Last – Second-last; Second – Third, Second-last – Third-last; ...”

And the most complex form of recitation was the *ghana-pāṭha*:

“w1-w2, w2-w1, w1-w2-w3, w3-w2-w1, w1-w2-w3; w2-w3, w3-w2, w2-w3-w4, w4-w3-w2, w2-w3-w4; ...”

This is how they memorized texts and used similar methods to memorize the mathematical ones too.⁴⁴

WRITTEN TRADITION

After 500 BCE, when the works started to be recorded in manuscripts, they were all written as Sūtras, i.e., the main statement of a principle (like verses) was the first and important part, and it was written very concisely and economically to help the student in their memorization. For instance, refer to the following statements from *Āryabhaṭīya* (Shukla and Sarma 38-40):

AREA OF A TRIANGLE

त्रिभुजस्य फलशरीरं समदलकोटीभुजार्धसंवर्गः ।

6. (a-b) The product of the perpendicular (dropped from the vertex on the base) and half the base gives the measure of the area of a triangle.

AREA OF A CIRCLE

समपरिणाहस्यार्धं विष्कम्भार्धहतमेव वृत्तफलम् ।

7. (a-b) Half of the circumference, multiplied by the semi-diameter certainly gives the area of a circle.

That is,

area of a circle = $\frac{1}{2} \times \text{circumference} \times \text{radius}$.

We see how beautiful and simple even their translations are, in their vocabulary. The first example is the area of a triangle, and we see how their statement not only corresponds to the correct formula that we use today ($1/2 \times \text{Base} \times \text{Height}$), but it gives the proper conceptual understanding of what the principle actually is, and yet sound so simple in the way it's written.

[The formula that we use today for the circle's area is πr^2 which is the same as above, if we calculate it: Circumference is $2\pi r$ so when you substitute this in the above formula, it gives us area = πr^2]

The reason the above principle is better in the way it's stated is that what we know today and what we are taught is πr^2 , which is okay to understand purely from a symbolic or a technical perspective. However, it is much nicer to know it conceptually with the 'words' being used first to describe the concept before using irrational symbols like π , which becomes a bit unrelatable to students, especially because it's the first time they are introduced to this symbol. The

teaching was, therefore, very root-focused, and the things were taught conceptually and not just superficially.

After the main statement (verse) and formula, the next thing was the ‘prose commentary’ that explained the statement or verse in detail and provided an example or working for the same. These prose commentaries helped to make sense out of the compressed formulae or statements. The good part about this was that testing the memory of the student wasn’t the only priority. Students weren’t always expected to rote-memorize the concepts ‘as they were designed’. They were free to express their versions and opinions about it, and sometimes the rules and statements were twisted on purpose to test whether the students had actually understood the concept as opposed to just ‘knowing’ it.⁴⁵

GOLDEN ERA

Indians reached the peak of their mathematics in the Classical Age – the Golden Era of Indian mathematics. The Gupta Dynasty (known as the Golden Age itself) that took over in 320 CE marks the beginning of this age. We see the finest mathematicians of India emerging in this period – Varahamihira (c.505 CE), Brahmagupta (c.598 CE), Bhāskara I (c.600), Mahavira (c.9th century), Āryabhaṭa II (c.920 CE), Bhāskara II (c.1114 CE), etc. spearheaded by the mighty Āryabhaṭa (c.476 CE). Their works and contributions collectively have been the major reason for India as a culture reaching its peak in terms of mathematical and scientific advancements and discoveries. The most significant and popular works of these mathematicians are – *Āryabhaṭīya*, Panchasiddhantika (by Varahamihira), Brāhmasphuṭasiddhānta (by Brahmagupta), and Sūryasiddhānta.

Āryabhaṭa was born before the others and his works were expounded and commentated by them, and although it sought of became a basis and influence for others, they very well had their own individual pathbreaking contributions that added to our culture’s mathematical expertise.

However, very little is known about how he came across these things, i.e., how all of this must have started. We directly have the statements in *Āryabhaṭīya* in which he mentioned the principles and properties regarding all mathematical topics. But we do not know how he reached there in the first place, or what raw work led him there.

THE LOOK OF IT

A question definitely arises here as to what their mathematics looked like. What language did they use? How did their numbers and symbols look like?

There was a system of numbers that was followed for writing mathematics. Especially when mathematical and astronomical works were facing challenges anyway on being expressed verbally before writing had begun. We have the *Kaṭapayādi* system that developed in around 500 CE, in which consonants beginning with Sanskrit letters ‘ka, ta, pa, ya...’ were used for the 10 decimal digits.⁴⁶ This became an interesting alpha-syllabic system in which letters (Sanskrit consonants) were used to represent numbers by using them in the correct sequence, thereby helping in the easy remembrance of numbers as words. Āryabhaṭa and other mathematicians had their own numeral tables under this system.

The *Brāhmī* script was one of the first scripts to be developed in the Mauryan period (3rd – 5th century BCE). The Bakhshali manuscript near Peshawar in Pakistan is the oldest extant mathematical document found in the Indian subcontinent in 1881, which is likely dated to 224-383 CE while some date it to 885-993 CE.⁴⁷ Āryabhaṭa used an even more complex system to represent astronomical numbers.

This gives us an idea of how mathematics at that time really looked like. The 10 decimal digits were written normally with a dot ‘.’ representing zero. The mathematical expressions were written without symbols (as they used words instead). The ‘+’ sign seen in the image did not represent addition but negative numbers (the sign was added after the negative number). The reason they chose this symbol for negative numbers is that the ‘+’ sign was actually derived from the letter ‘r’ that stood for ‘*rhna*’ in Sanskrit meaning ‘negative’. For the other signs like addition, ‘yu’ (for *yuta* or “adding”) was used. For showing operations like the square root, ‘mu’ (for *mula* or “rooting”) was used.⁴⁸ For the term ‘x’ that we use everywhere in algebra, the word used in *Āryabhaṭīya* is ‘*Gulikā*’, meaning a ‘*thing of an unknown value*’.⁴⁹

WRITING MATERIAL

Another intriguing question that often arises when we study any ancient field is how these people wrote and especially what did they write on. Long before the advent of paper, writings were done on the *Bhurjapatras* (i.e., birch barks; seen in the picture above).

Other than this, there were plenty of other writing materials used. Rock edicts from the ancient Mauryan times, inscribed bricks, ivory bars, conch shells, are some examples. Gold plates were often used to write royal letters. Cloth was also used in the BCE to write on. These were well-beaten cotton cloths that were first layered with wheat or rice pulp and then polished with a conch shell after they had dried up.⁵⁰

Wooden boards and tablets were also widely used for writing. The characters were written using chalk or ink. An amusing fact related to this is that the mathematical calculations were also called ‘*dhuli-karma*’ or dust-work. This is because the boards were layered with a dust spread, and fingers, hands, or pieces of reed were used to write on this layer of dust, thereby using them as dust-boards.⁵¹

ALGEBRA

The origins of algebra in India can also be traced back to the *Śulba Sūtras*. The exact origins are unknown but we see it was already being practiced by the Jain mathematicians and *Āryabhaṭa* too, in his time. Later, by the 7th and 8th centuries CE, algebra and arithmetic both

started to emerge further as well-established fields. Algebra was called the ‘*bīja-gaṇita*’, literally meaning ‘mathematics of the seeds’ – referring to the unknowns with potential to generate (such as in the case of the solutions of equations).⁵² In other perspectives, ‘*bīja*’ also refers to ‘analysis’, and ‘*gaṇita*’ means the ‘science of calculation’, together meaning ‘the science of analytical calculation’. Algebra and arithmetic have also been named ‘*avyakta gaṇita*’ (science of calculation with the ‘unknown’) and ‘*vyakta gaṇita*’ (science of calculation with the ‘known’) respectively.⁵³

A popular misconception often exists among students about how we don’t use algebra in our daily life, whereas, in reality, algebra is one of the most basic and primitive ways to find solutions to the problems by using a random letter ‘*x*’ instead of the unknown thing that we have to find in any given situation. From something as basic as cooking to calculating profits and losses, speed-distance-time, ratios, and proportions, we use algebra in everything, often unknowingly. That is also how algebra started back in the time. The scholars started creating situations in which people were given a few things but not the main element that was needed. So, the way to find the unknown element was to use ‘*x*’ (or any term in its place). This is why these problems were created, as they replicated life, and the problems that come with it.

We do get to see some examples of this. Back in 1150 CE, Bhāskaracharya wrote a book for his daughter Lilavati to teach her different topics in mathematics, naming the book after her.⁵⁴ It has problems asked in a word-problem format where they used the concept of ‘*x*’ to solve the unknown value that was required. Here’s a look at one of them:

“From a bunch of lotuses, one-third were offered to Lord Shiva (त्रिनयन), one-fifth to Lord Vishnu (हरि), one-sixth to Surya Deva, one-fourth to the goddess. The remaining six were offered to the Guru. Tell me quickly the number of lotuses in the bunch”

Let the number of lotuses be ‘*x*’

Then, the number of lotuses offered to Lord Shiva will be $x/3$

The number of lotuses offered to Lord Vishnu will be $x/5$

The number of lotuses offered to Surya deva will be $x/6$

The number of lotuses offered to the Goddess will be $x/4$

Thus, we have

$$x - \frac{x}{3} - \frac{x}{5} - \frac{x}{6} - \frac{x}{4} = 6$$

$$\therefore \frac{60x - 20x - 12x - 10x - 15x}{60} = 6$$

$$\therefore x = 120$$

Thus, there were 120 lotuses in the bunch.

Another example of a question he gave (Feel free to solve):

One-half and one-third of the half of a group of elephants went into a cave. One-sixth and one-seventh of one-sixth were drinking water from a river. One-eighth and one-ninth of one-eighth were playing in a pond full of lotuses. The king of elephants was walking with three female elephants. Tell me how many elephants were there in the group? (Halai)

[Ans: $x = 1008$]

MATHEMATICIANS & THEIR CONTRIBUTIONS

ĀRYABHAṬA

In the Ganita section of *Āryabhaṭīya*, Āryabhaṭa mentions the basic arithmetical operators like squaring and cubing numbers along with calculating their roots.

He contributes to the field of mensuration by giving the correct formulae for the area of circle, triangle, trapezium, volume of a sphere, etc. that correspond to the present-day formulae for the same. For instance, this is the formula he gives for the area of a trapezium:

Today, we use the same formula for finding the trapezium's area: $1/2 \times$ sum of parallel sides \times height.

His book gives various different formulae for arithmetic progression, including finding the number of terms of an AP, and also finding the sum of the 'n' terms:⁵⁵

Let S be the sum of the series

$$a + (a + d) + (a + 2d) + (a + 3d) + \dots \text{to } n \text{ terms.}$$

Then

$$n = \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\sqrt{8dS + (2a - d)^2} - 2a}{d} + 1 \right].$$

the sum of the n terms

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (a + pd) + (a + \overline{p+1}a) + \dots + \{a + (p+n-1)d\} \\
 & = n \left\{ a + \left(\frac{n-1}{2} + p \right) d \right\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Simplifying fractions by making equal denominators (continued fractions) was also given by him:⁵⁹

छेदगुणं सच्छेदं परस्परं तत् सवर्णत्वम् ॥ २७ ॥

27. (c-d) Multiply the numerator as also the denominator of each fraction by the denominator of the other fraction ; then the (given) fractions are reduced to a common denominator.¹

That is,

$$\frac{a}{b} + \frac{c}{d} = \frac{ad}{bd} + \frac{bc}{bd} = \frac{ad+bc}{bd},$$

$$\frac{a}{b} - \frac{c}{d} = \frac{ad}{bd} - \frac{bc}{bd} = \frac{ad-bc}{bd}.$$

Another amazing method not taught much in academics today is the ‘method of inversion’ that he came up with.⁶⁰ In this method, we reverse the mathematical operations to reach the answer that cannot be solved in a linear manner. Here’s an example he gave to explain this fascinating principle:

Example. A number is multiplied by 2 ; then increased by 1 ; then divided by 5 ; then multiplied by 3 ; then diminished by 2 ; and then divided by 7 ; the result (thus obtained) is 1. Say what is the initial number.

Starting from the last number 1, in the reverse order, inverting the operations, the result is

$$1 \times 7, + 2, \div 3, \times 5, -1, \div 2, i. e. 7.$$

If we tried solving the question normally by using ‘ x ’, like ‘ $x \times 2, + 1, \div 5, \dots$ ’ and so on, we reach the answer in a tiresome manner with complex bracketing, shifting, solving, etc. But on inverting the signs and reversing the order, it helps us reach the answer easily, as seen above.

Āryabhaṭa dealt with linear equations during his time, and he derived a unique method of his own to find the solutions of an equation of the form $ax + by = c$ [where ‘ a ’ and ‘ b ’ and ‘ c ’ are whole numbers seeking values for the variables x and y]. He named it the ‘*kuttaka*’ method (pulverizer), and it was an extensive method of continued division that was carried out until the solutions were obtained. He gave rules for solving problems based on ‘interest’ – and this is what led him to do quadratic equations and find their solutions.

In the field of geometry too, Āryabhaṭa mentioned a lot of theorems related to the properties of circles and triangles. He is obviously, in popular history, credited the most for the invention of the number ‘zero’. However, we see above in the paper how zero as a concept already existed before. What Āryabhaṭa did was that he used it as a placeholder number in the decimal number system. It was only later in the 7th century that we see Brahmagupta starting to use zero more independently. Initially, it was denoted as a dot and the Bakhshali manuscript is the oldest known example that shows the same.

Another one of his many achievements was to find out the *sine* functions and use them in astronomy. In fact, one of the reasons trigonometry as a separate discipline was developed is because these ancient astronomers realized that they couldn’t measure stars, planets and the distance between them in a linear fashion since the sky is curved. This means, the stars in the sky might only appear to be in a straight line. Imagine this – if there’s a star right above our head, and a star at the horizon level, then the motion of our arm from the star above our head to the star at the horizon will be a curved angle – and this angle is what went on to become ‘ θ ’ (*theta*).⁶¹

We have been reading about the achievements of Āryabhaṭa since the start of this paper, by referring to this *Āryabhaṭīya*, and as much as the content has been fascinating, so was his age,

when he discovered all this. Āryabhaṭa was merely a 23-year-old youngster when he authored *Āryabhaṭīya*. All this mountain of knowledge, in the brain of a 23-year-old. Below is a Sutra regarding his birth that he mentions in *Āryabhaṭīya*:⁶²

षष्ट्यब्दानां षष्टयेदा व्यतीतास्त्रयश्च युगपादाः ।

त्र्यधिका विंशतिरब्दास्तदेह मम जन्मनोऽतीताः ॥ १० ॥

When sixty times sixty years and three quarter *yugas* (of the current *yuga*) had elapsed, twentythree years had then passed since my birth.

This stanza mentions that 3600 years had been passed since the beginning of the current Kaliyuga. And after the calculations, this data corresponds to the date of March 21, Sunday, 499 CE. Āryabhaṭa, in a stylish fashion, wrote that he was 23 years of age on this day, meaning he was born on March 21, 476 CE.

VARAHAMIHIRA

Varahamihira, (c.505-587 CE), the next important mathematician-astronomer after Āryabhaṭa, made some prominent contributions during his time. He is said to have lived in and around the city of Ujjain in India. He was influenced by different *siddhantas* or treatises by different personalities and wrote the Panchasiddhantika, which is a text that's a compilation of five major treatises of different schools of astronomy that were prevalent in India – Sūryasiddhānta (treatise of the Sun), Romaka Siddhanta (treatise of the Romans), Paulisa Siddhanta (treatise based on a Greek source), Vasishtha Siddhanta (treatise of the sage Vasishtha), Paitāmaha Siddhanta (treatise of the *Brahma*). Together they came to be known as 'the 5 Astronomical Canons of India'.

His *Bṛhat Samhitā* is an encyclopedic work dealing with diverse topics including how to sharpen swords, how to ascertain the value of precious metals and stones, how to make trees bear fruit out of season, how to distinguish the good breeds of animals, and how to divine the location of water. It also discusses the nature and structure of temples, palaces,

and houses. It gives an explanation of seasons and discusses meteorological issues such as the correlation between the clouds, winds, and amount of rainfall.⁶³

Those who are well-versed with trigonometry, know that one of the most famous identities taught in it is $\sin^2 x + \cos^2 x = 1$. The man behind this was none other than him. He contributed to a few other identities along with this, and also gave sine and cosine tables up to four decimal places of accuracy.

BRAHMAGUPTA

Brahmagupta (c.598-668 CE), wrote popular works like *Brāhmasphuṭasiddhānta* (628 CE) and *Khaṇḍakhādya* (665 CE). Brahmagupta's algebra was quite a level higher, complex and extensive. He did a detailed work on linear and quadratic equations in *Brāhmasphuṭasiddhānta*, which he wrote at the age of 30. He explained problems to find solutions for constant values (known as *rupas*) out of the coefficients (the number attached to the 'x' term) of the unknowns (x). For instance, for a general linear equation $bx + c = dx + e$ in which c and e are constants or *rupas* and b and d are the coefficients of the common term 'x' that has to be found, the solution is:

$$x = \frac{e - c}{b - d}$$

The above example is one of his most basic ones to get an idea. His other works on quadratic equations are of a very advanced level, where he has given solutions for quadratic equations like $ax^2 + bx = c$:

$$x = \frac{\pm\sqrt{4ac+b^2}-b}{2a} \quad \text{and} \quad x = \frac{\pm\sqrt{ac+\frac{b^2}{4}}-\frac{b}{2}}{a}$$

Brahmagupta is credited with the first clear description of the quadratic formula (the solution of the quadratic equation) in his main work, the *Brāhmasphuṭasiddhānta*. One of the most famous quadratic equation formulas, $x = -b \pm \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}/2$, was also extensively explained and described by Brahmagupta (although in words). The formula he gave was:

$$x = \sqrt{c.4a + b^2} - b/2a$$

Along with quadratic equations, he also gave solutions for indeterminate equations (equations which have more than one solution) of the first degree (Ex. $ax - by = c$).

A unique feature of Brahmagupta's mathematics was that his algebra used to be syncopated. Syncopated algebra is basically the kind of mathematics in which there is limited symbolism used and it does not contain all the characteristics of symbolic algebra.⁶⁴ Everything is mostly written out in words, except that some abbreviations are used for certain recurring operations.

There are two important facts about his *Brāhmasphuṭasiddhānta* related to the digit '0'. This book becomes the first one to apply arithmetic manipulations to '0' and to 'negative numbers'. And not just this, it is also the earliest known text to treat '0' as an independent number of its own, instead of using it as a companion-digit to make sense out of other numbers (something that the ancient Babylonians did).

In fact, he was the first one to attempt to divide any non-zero number by zero, and he did not fully commit but claimed the answer to be infinity, i.e., $\frac{n}{0} = \infty$. In mathematics, till date, the answer remains the same. His answer matches the modern understanding of the same, making us realize their advanced understanding even for such abstract concepts.

When it comes to geometry, his most infamous discovery is his theorem on cyclic quadrilaterals.⁶⁵

If we know the values of the sides of the quadrilateral, then Brahmagupta gives both an approximate and an exact formula to find out the area of the figure. As per the above figure, the formula for the approximate area of the quadrilateral ABCD would be: $\frac{p+r}{2} \times \frac{q+s}{2}$

Brahmagupta was the first one to define gravity as an attractive force, and he was the one to coin the term ‘*gurutvākarṣaṇam*’ for the same. His words, when translated, say “*The earth on all its sides is the same; all people on the earth stand upright, and all heavy things fall down to the earth by a law of nature, for it is the nature of the earth to attract and to keep things, as it is the nature of water to flow...*”⁶⁶

These texts became very influential within India, and their Arab translations and adaptations introduced Indian astronomy to the Arabs. Few decades after Brahmagupta died, Sindh came under the Arab Caliphate in 712 CE. The court of Al-Mansur (second Caliph of the Abbasid Caliphate), received astronomical texts from an astrologer Kanaka that also included the texts of Brahmagupta. These texts were translated into Arabic by Muhammad-al-Fazari who was an astronomer in his court, and the text was given the infamous name ‘*Sindhind*’.⁶⁷ Brahmagupta was the one who taught Arabs mathematics before they got acquainted with Greek science.

BHĀSKARA I

Bhāskara I (c.600-680) was another popular astronomer and mathematician who was the first one to write numbers in the Hindu-Arabic decimal system by using a circle to write ‘0’. All the later astronomers wrote commentaries and worked upon the works of the astronomers that preceded them, and Bhāskara I also looked into Āryabhaṭa’s work deeply and gave his commentary on the same. He worked on the sine functions given by him and improved them up to a great extent, and became very well known for his rational approximation of the sine function. He explained the problems of indeterminate equations and trigonometric formulae.⁶⁸ His commentary on *Āryabhaṭīya* was called *Āryabhaṭīyabhāṣya*.

Then from the 9th to 12th centuries, there were other popular mathematicians like Mahavira (c.800-870) who wrote a book called *Ganit Saar Sangraha*, in which he wrote on topics like zero, squares, cubes, plane and solid geometry. Other mathematicians like Shridhara, Manjula, Āryabhaṭa II, Bhāskara II worked on a lot of topics ranging from quadratic equations, exponents, to logarithms, interest computations and surds.

DECIMAL NUMBER SYSTEM

On a superficial level, India may be remembered for just the major discoveries like the zero. However, the decimal number system that we use everywhere in the world today was also first recorded first in Indian mathematics.⁶⁹ The usage of this system that came from Indian mathematics was turning point in world mathematics; it changed the way mathematics was done.

The Indian works were translated into the Arab versions from where they eventually went to Europe. Indian mathematicians were using the system in the 5th century CE. In Europe, the old complex system was followed till the 12th century until the Europeans learnt the new system from the Arabs, who themselves learnt it through the translated Indian works. In fact, Arab writers such as Al-Masudi and Al-Biruni give the credit for the discovery of the decimal system to the 'Hindus' in their works.⁷⁰

INJUSTICE

Our original historical narrative was supposed to be perfect until a complete distortion of our history took place due to the different invasions and rules that took place. This is why, what we study today, or rather what the world studies about us today, is a distorted version of history that has not been written by us. We have not been the directors of our own movie. They tell us who we are, rather than us. The British rewrote our history for their civil servants and hence described us as a backward, primitive, and an uncivilized society. This same mentality was followed by the Christian missionaries and the Eurocentric people who came after them. This is especially after William Jones (British philologist) talked about how Sanskrit, Latin and Greek had a common root language, and they might have all been related to Gothic, Celtic and Persian languages. The problem didn't just end here. These different ideologies affected India's constitution too, wherein our original Indian ideology was suppressed and discarded under the pretext of beginning a classless future with a new beginning to make modern laws.⁷¹

Apart from this, we also have the 'enforced narration' as compared to the evidence-based one. According to it, apparently the Aryans from Central Asia invaded the Harrapan

civilization and became civilized after India, particularly Magadha, came in contact with the Greeks in 300 BCE. This nonsensical philosophy finally comes to a bizarre conclusion implying that the Indian civilization is a recent one, and that the entire knowledge that we've had in astronomy or mathematics was received from the Greeks and the Babylonians.⁷²

CONCLUSION

As for the achievements of ancient Indians, the fact that they got such precise results with such high accuracy is truly remarkable. The reason it is remarkable is because of the time period that this took place in. Because even though we know the period, when we read about these milestones, we often tend to overlook or not 'feel' or imagine the life back then. We don't realize how the magnitude of their achievements just doubles up, because of the period they did all this in. Especially with no technological advantage like we have today.

For instance, in the astronomy section, when we saw how they used some fascinating units to measure things around them, like linking human respiration with time and using it to measure angles in the sky, it's truly mind-blowing to let this sink in and realize that these are real facts. What makes these calculations remarkable and epic is that these were done without the aid of any modern devices we use today. Indeed, their time was limited in technology, but it did not limit them, in achieving their purpose and making the best out of what they had.

In fact, that's just a reminder of how history is. The further you go back in time, the smarter the people were. Convenience rusts man's skill. History teaches us that intelligence is always inversely proportional to time. The more convenient and easier any age is, the average benchmark and the intellectual standard of man will always get lower. Because most of what could be discovered, already has, so the window of what new has to be explored grows shorter comparatively with time, as man's discoveries have always grown exponentially compared to time.

Today, in a free world, it is very easy to study these things mentioned in the paper. We have the internet, books, etc. to read from, but it has been a really tough journey for these sciences to survive their essence through the different periods and dominating philosophies like the colonial, Eurocentric, etc., as they wrote history from their perspective to show India as a backward culture. Despite all this, if so much material from our past still exists, one can only

imagine how different the current reality and our knowledge about the sciences would have been if India as a land would have not gone through this turmoil. Despite these invasions and rules, despite the destruction, fabrication, and the adulteration of our sciences, this leftover material that we still have today is enough to prove that our sciences have been one of the most advanced of all, being much ahead of many cultures and civilizations that claim to be superior. Its grandeur goes beyond proving.

When it comes to getting fair credit, the problem discussed is always about how Indians did not write their things down like proofs, unlike the Europeans. But was this really a problem? Not writing things down came from a superior computing mindset that was advanced enough to memorize and pass on knowledge orally. Secondly, as mentioned above, the applications of these computations and literary works were only done by the scholarly priests, so they were not meant to be open for public education. Their memorization skills were just off the charts. It was a superhuman skill in itself to not just calculate and apply these studies mentally for themselves, but also to pass it down generationally. The standard of teaching and learning was high enough to cause disbelief, let alone crediting it fairly.

Despite how we are seen or whatever credit we receive, it mustn't be done for the desire to be validated externally. The point is to never do it for those reasons. Doing so only puts them at a higher authority, proving their stance correct.

We must celebrate, cherish and remember our history for what it is, and be proud of what it has been. This is the way we do justice to it. This paper is an attempt to promote the right kind of education that our future needs.

It was an honor writing about these great men of India. Their legacy was a motivation in making a small contribution from my side to their work, and paying them a heartfelt tribute by spreading their education to as many as I can.

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- 1 See Shukla and Sarma, *Aryabhatiya of Āryabhaṭa: 3 Volumes*, p. 69. ‘Him’ refers to lord *Brahma*.
 - 2 “Shulba Sutras”
 - 3 "Hindu Astrology." *Wikipedia*, 8 Jan. 2024, en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hindu_astrology.
 - 4 See Shukla and Sarma, “The Gola Section”, *Aryabhatiya*, p.119
 - 5 Sangam Talks. "Ancient Indic Astronomy." *YouTube*
 - 6 Shukla and Sarma, *Aryabhatiya*, p. 8
 - 7 Shukla and Sarma, *Aryabhatiya*, p. 9
 - 8 Shukla and Sarma, *Aryabhatiya*, p. 6
 - 9 ‘Revolution Number of the Moon’ as per the table above
 - 10 Shukla and Sarma, p. 14
 - 11 Shukla and Sarma, p. 13
 - 12 Shukla and Sarma, p. 8
 - 13 ‘*nr*’ also referring to ‘Male’ in Hindi
 - 14 Shukla and Sarma, p. 15
 - 15 Sangam Talks. "Ancient Indic Astronomy." *YouTube*
 - 16 Devdutt Pattanaik, *Jaya*, 2010.
 - 17 Sangam Talks. "Ancient Indic Astronomy." *YouTube*
 - 18 Chris Lintott, "Andromeda-Milky Way Collision," BBC Sky at Night Magazine, June 25, 2024
 - 19 Sangam Talks. "Ancient Indic Astronomy." *YouTube*
 - 20 "Andromeda." *Encyclopaedia Britannica*
 - 21 Sangam Talks. “Ancient Indic Roots of Knowledge Systems” *YouTube*
 - 22 A Sanskrit treatise whose authorship remains a mystery. It is considered to be a compilation from different sources, including Maya Asura (divine architect of the Asuras in Hindu mythology), Lāṭadeva (a student of Āryabhaṭa I or II), and Surya (Sun God).
 - 23 Sangam Talks. "Ancient Indic Astronomy." *YouTube*
 - 24 See Library of Congress, *What Is the Transit of Venus?*
 - 25 ARIES, *Great Conjunction of Jupiter and Saturn*.
 - 26 Sangam Talks. "Ancient Indic Astronomy." *YouTube*
 - 27 “Indian Astronomy.” *Wikipedia*
 - 28 See Roy, “Zero Points of Vedic Astronomy.”
 - 29 Sangam Talks. "Ancient Indic Astronomy." *YouTube*

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- 30 See Singh, *A History of Ancient and Early Medieval India*.
- 31 Barua, "A Brief History of Ancient Indian Mathematics."
- 32 —, "A Brief History of Ancient Indian Mathematics."
- 33 Maheshwari, "Mathematics of the Vedas."
- 34 "Indian Mathematics." *Wikipedia*
- 35 Barua, "A Brief History of Ancient Indian Mathematics."
- 36 Admin et al., "FIRE ALTARS OF THE VEDAS."
- 37 Barua, "A Brief History of Ancient Indian Mathematics."
- 38 "Indian Mathematics," *Wikipedia*.
- 39 "Śulba Sūtras," *Wikipedia*, en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Shulba_Sutras.
- 40 Barua, "A Brief History of Ancient Indian Mathematics."
- 41 Shukla and Sarma, *Op.cit.* p. 45
- 42 Barua, "A Brief History of Ancient Indian Mathematics."
- 43 "Indian Mathematics," *Wikipedia*.
- 44 "Indian Mathematics."
- 45 Plofker, "Indian Mathematics."
- 46 —, "Indian Mathematics."
- 47 "Indian Mathematics," *Wikipedia*.
- 48 Plofker, "Indian Mathematics."
- 49 Shukla and Sarma, *Aryabhatiya*, p. 73
- 50 "Writing Materials in Ancient India."
- 51 "Writing Materials in Ancient India."
- 52 "Indian Mathematics," *Wikipedia*.
- 53 Halai, "Algebra Originated in India."
- 54 —, "Algebra Originated in India."
- 55 Shukla and Sarma, *Aryabhatiya*, p. 62-64
- 56 Shukla and Sarma, p. 68
- 57 Sangam Talks. "Ancient Indic Astronomy." *YouTube*
- 58 Shukla and Sarma, p. 69
- 59 Shukla and Sarma, p. 70
- 60 Shukla and Sarma, p. 71
- 61 Sangam Talks. "Ancient Indic Astronomy." *YouTube*
- 62 Shukla and Sarma, p. 95
- 63 Singh, *A History of Ancient and Early Medieval India*.

64 "History of Algebra." *Wikipedia*.

65 A cyclic quadrilateral is basically a quadrilateral subtended inside a circle, with all its four vertices touching the circumference of the circle.

66 "Brahmagupta." *Wikipedia*.

67 "Brahmagupta." *Wikipedia*.

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